

Characterization of commercial fish *pâtés*: toward the development of novel fish-based spreads

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the textural and sensory properties of commercial fish *pâtés* available on the Serbian market to identify differences in quality and consumer-relevant characteristics. 14 *pâté* samples made from marine (tuna, salmon, mackerel, hake) and freshwater (trout) fish were analyzed. Texture profile analysis included measurements of firmness and work of shear, while sensory evaluation was conducted by a trained panel, focusing on hardness, spreadability, graininess, color uniformity, taste, and smell. Significant variability ($p < 0.05$) was observed among the samples, indicating diverse formulation strategies. Tuna- and salmon-based *pâtés* achieved the highest overall acceptability due to their appealing flavor and appearance. In contrast, trout-based *pâtés* exhibited more balanced texture attributes, with sensory and instrumental data aligning closely with ideal values. These findings provide useful guidance for the development of novel fish *pâtés* using underutilized species such as freshwater bream (*Abramis brama*), which have been identified as key low-trophic species within the HEU project IMPRESS. The results highlight the importance of optimizing textural properties to enhance consumer acceptability.

1. Introduction

The global *pâté* market was valued at US\$ 1.74 billion in 2023 and is projected to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 4.9% from 2024 to 2030, reaching an estimated US\$ 2.44 billion by 2030 (Grand View Research, 2024). This growth is driven by evolving consumer preferences for convenient, ready-to-eat foods, the rise of snacking culture, and the increasing adoption of diverse culinary trends (Engelen & de Wijk, 2012). In Serbia, the *pâté* and spread category recorded a 1% increase in volume and a 6.3% increase in value between March 2024 and February 2025, with 43%

of total sales generated through promotional activities. Notably, fish *pâtés* account for 11% of total volume sales but contribute 18% to total value sales, indicating strong market potential for premium fish-based products (Retail Zoom, 2025).

Fish *pâtés* offer significant nutritional benefits compared to meat-based alternatives. These attributes make them a valuable addition to diets, particularly in regions with low fish consumption. Given that consumers with a strong interest in food quality perceive fish more positively than meat in terms of freshness, taste, and safety (Torrisen & Onozaka, 2017), the development of premium fish *pâtés* may

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particularly appeal to this market segment. However, the Serbian market is predominantly supplied with marine fish *pâtés* (e.g., tuna – *Thunnus albacares*, hake – *Merluccius hubbsi*, salmon – *Salmo salar*, Atlantic mackerel – *Scomber scombrus*) and freshwater (trout – *Oncorhynchus mykiss*), while low-trophic species such as bream (*Abramis brama*) and roach (*Rutilus rutilus*) remain underutilized. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization, global per capita fish consumption surpassed 20.6 kg in 2021, more than doubling since the 1960s (FAO, 2024). In contrast, fish intake in Serbia remains significantly lower, averaging approximately 7 kg per person annually. Marine fish and seafood accounted for 92.80% of the total fish and fish product supply on the Serbian market, whereas freshwater fish represented only 7.14% (Janjić et al., 2024). Freshwater fish, although less studied than marine species, are a valuable nutritional source due to their lower fat and sodium content, lower mercury risk, and richness in high-quality proteins and micronutrients. These attributes make them a safe and nutritionally beneficial choice for diverse populations (Lámfalussy et al., 2025; Regal Springs, 2025; Ahmed et al., 2022; Mielcarek et al., 2020).

This study aimed to conduct an evaluation of sensory and textural properties of 14 commercial fish *pâtés* available on the Serbian market to identify their “strengths and weaknesses”. The results will serve as a basis for developing of an innovative fish spread from underutilized species (freshwater bream) by guiding the optimization of its formulation and processing parameters in accordance with consumer preferences and current market trends.

2. Materials and methods

2.1.1. Sample collection

A total of 14 commercial fish *pâté* samples were collected from retail markets in Serbia between March and April 2025. The samples were selected to represent a diverse range of products available on the Serbian market, including both marine (tuna – *Thunnus albacares*, hake – *Merluccius hubbsi*, salmon – *Salmo salar*, Atlantic mackerel – *Scomber scombrus*) and freshwater (trout – *Oncorhynchus mykiss*) fish-based *pâtés*. Selection criteria were product availability in major retail channels (hypermarkets, supermarkets, and medium-sized stores), popularity based on sales data (Retail Zoom, 2025), and variation in fish species and brands.

2.1.2. Sensory evaluation

Sensory evaluation was conducted by 10 trained assessors (ISO 8586:2023 ; Sensory analysis, 2023) in a standardized sensory lab (SRPS EN ISO 8589:2015 ; Sensory analysis, 2015), using seven-point (7) scales (SRPS ISO 4121:2013 ; Sensory analysis, 2013) to assess color uniformity, taste, smell, surface homogeneity, spreadability, graininess, hardness, and overall acceptability, following the protocol described by Nikolić et al. (2018).

2.1.3. Textural analysis

Texture analysis of the top-rated sensory samples was performed using a TA.XT Plus Texture Analyzer (Stable Micro Systems, UK), following the Margarine Spreadability protocol (MAR4_SR.PRJ), as described by Županjac et al., 2023. A Spreadability Rig HDP/SR was used at 22 °C with a 5 kg load cell. Test speeds were set to 1.0 mm/s (pre-test), 3.0 mm/s (test), and 10.0 mm/s (post-test). Firmness and shearing work were determined based on the force during probe penetration.

2.1.4. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was done using One-way ANOVA (Statistica 14.0.0.15, TIBCO Software Inc., USA). Duncan’s post hoc test was performed for comparison of mean values. Differences were considered significant at $p < 0.05$.

3. Results and discussion

Statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were observed among the *pâté* samples in both firmness and work of shear (Table 1), indicating a broad textural range among the commercial products. Sample 139 (salmon *pâté*) exhibited the highest firmness (414 ± 16.9 g) and work of shear (417 ± 22.7 g sec), suggesting a dense and cohesive texture that may hinder spreadability. In contrast, sample 571 (tuna and mackerel) had the lowest values (firmness, 49.4 ± 0.52 g; work of shear, 38.1 ± 1.80 g sec), reflecting a very soft and easily spreadable product. The variability in firmness and spreadability among *pâté* samples can be attributed to differences in protein content and composition (Trindade et al., 2023; Zheng et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2010), fat content and structure (Martínez et al., 2025 ; Botella-Martínez et al., 2024; Lima et al., 2022; Tiensa

et al., 2017), water content (Mancera-Rodriguez et al., 2022), use of different emulsifiers (Baechle et al., 2025; Youssef & Barbut, 2011; 2010), and processing methods (Pětová et al., 2024; Lazárková et al., 2023; Aydın et al., 2020), as well as storage and serving temperature, which have been shown to significantly affect the rheological and sensory characteristics of high-fat emulsified products (Yang et al., 2024). Proteins derived from different fish species (Yi-Li et al., 2025; Fernandes et al., 2024; Traina et al., 2024; Ahmed et al., 2022; Tilami et al., 2018) exhibit distinct gelation behavior, emulsifying capacity, and water-holding ability, which significantly influence the texture of fish-based spreads. Higher protein and fat levels generally contribute to a denser and more cohesive texture, while increased moisture and finer particle size favor softer and more easily spreadable products.

Samples 383, 428, and 329 exhibited intermediate firmness (276 ± 16.1 to 288 ± 7.73 g) and work of shear (274 ± 13.4 to 291 ± 15.2 g sec), likely indicating a balanced texture that aligns with typical consumer expectations.

Sample 555, although soft (146 ± 24.7 g), exhibited high work of shear (245.51 ± 33.93 g sec), indicating a soft yet less spreadable pâté touch (Di Monaco et al., 2008; Szczesniak, 2002). This is often linked to cohesive or elastic matrices that increase resistance to deformation, as confirmed in studies on

fish pâtés and fat-based products (Raničević et al., 2020; Lončarević et al., 2013).

Variations in firmness and spreadability were also observed within the same fish pâté types. For example, significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in firmness and work of shear were observed among tuna pâté samples, with firmness ranging from 167 ± 7.11 g to 327 ± 21.4 g. Higher values of both parameters indicate a denser, more cohesive texture that may reduce spreadability, while lower values suggest a softer, more easily spreadable product. These variations likely reflect different formulation and processing approaches (Pětová et al., 2024; Lazárková et al., 2023). Similarly, mixed fish pâtés made from tuna and mackerel (samples 149 and 571) showed statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$). Sample 149 exhibited high firmness and work of shear values (310 ± 28.9 g and 301 ± 35.7 g sec, respectively), indicating a dense and cohesive texture, while sample 571 had the lowest values (49.4 ± 0.52 g and 38.1 ± 1.80 g sec, respectively), reflecting a very soft and easily spreadable product. These differences highlight the impact of ingredient ratios and processing methods, emphasizing the need for formulation standardization to optimize textural properties (Martínez et al., 2025; Botella-Martínez et al., 2024; Mancera-Rodriguez et al., 2022; Tiensa et al., 2017). Among the salmon pâtés, samples 857 (firmness 295 ± 4.55 g; work of shear 262 ± 6.90 g sec) and

Table 1. Texture (firmness and work of shear) for fish pâté samples

Sample	Firmness (g)	Work of Shear (g sec)
139 - salmon	414 ± 16.9^g	417 ± 22.7^g
428 - tuna	276 ± 16.1^d	274 ± 13.4^{def}
571 - tuna and mackerel	49.4 ± 0.52^a	38.1 ± 1.80^a
965 - trout	151 ± 7.11^b	152 ± 8.03^b
711 - tuna	327 ± 21.4^f	335 ± 1.80^f
383 - tuna	288 ± 7.73^{de}	286 ± 12.6^{ef}
627 - tuna	172 ± 15.3^b	163 ± 20.4^b
334 - tuna	167 ± 7.11^b	169 ± 13.2^b
555 - trout	146 ± 24.6^c	245 ± 33.9^c
149 - tuna and mackerel	310 ± 28.9^{ef}	301 ± 35.6^f
314 - salmon	229 ± 7.25^c	223 ± 7.38^c
857 - salmon	295 ± 4.55^{de}	262 ± 6.90^d
222 - tuna	284 ± 8.13^{de}	299 ± 12.4^f
329 - hake	281 ± 12.2^d	291 ± 15.2^{ef}

Legend: ^{a,b,c,d,e,f,g} Different letters in the column mean that pâtés are statistically different

314 (firmness 229 ± 7.25 g; work of shear 223 ± 7.38 g sec) showed similar texture and spreadability, while sample 139 (firmness 414 ± 16.92 g; work of shear 417 ± 22.7 g sec) exhibited significantly higher firmness and shear work, indicating a denser and less spreadable product.

Sensory evaluation is a valuable tool for predicting the overall acceptability of spreadable food products. It has been widely applied in the assessment of fish-, meat-, and plant-based spreads (Mancera-Rodriguez et al., 2022; Ranilović et al., 2020; Branciarri et al., 2019; Difonzo et al., 2019; Kim et al., 2018). Figure 1 (panels A-C) presents the sensory evaluation findings described in the following section. Overall scores ranged from 4.4 (samples 329, 571) to 6.4 (222, 428), with tuna and salmon pâtés rated highest, aligning with previous findings on consumer preferences (Nguyen et al., 2023; Budhathoki et al., 2022).

Texture attributes varied: sample 139 showed slightly excessive hardness (5.4) and spreadability (5.1), while sample 571 had notably low scores (1.3), indicating an overly soft texture and poor homogeneity (2.3). Graininess was near optimal for most, though 383 (4.3) was slightly coarse, and 571 overly smooth (1.9). Color uniformity was generally high,

with 139 scoring 7.0, though some samples, like 329 and 627, showed minor surface heterogeneity.

Lightness varied; 329, 383, and 571 appeared too light, suggesting possible dilution, while 334, 428, and 857 were slightly darker. Taste and smell were scored highest for 139, 314, and 965 (≥ 6.6), especially trout pâtés (555, 965), which also showed ideal hardness and spreadability, though with slightly lower overall acceptability compared to marine fish pâtés (Lámfalusy et al., 2025; Stojanovska et al., 2022).

Results highlight that, while marine fish pâtés, particularly tuna and salmon, had higher overall acceptability, the freshwater trout pâtés excelled in textural and flavor attributes important for consumer satisfaction.

4. Conclusion

This study provided a detailed evaluation of the textural and sensory properties of commercial fish pâtés available on the Serbian market. The results revealed substantial variability among products, reflecting heterogeneity in formulation strategies and a general lack of standardization regarding texture and consumer-relevant attributes. Instrumental measurements of firmness and spreadability

Figure 1. A) Hardness, spreadability and graininess; B) Surface homogeneity, lightness and color uniformity; C) Overall acceptability taste and smell (222 – Tuna; 383 – Tuna; 334 – Tuna; 428 – Tuna; 627 – Tuna; 711 – Tuna; 329 – Hake; 139 – Salmon; 314 – Salmon; 857 – Salmon; 571 – Tuna and Mackerel; 149 – Tuna and Mackerel; 555 – Trout; 965 – Trout.)

showed significant differences between the samples, being largely in agreement with sensory perceptions of hardness and ease of spreading. Marine fish pâtés, particularly those made from tuna and salmon were generally rated higher in terms of overall acceptability, primarily due to favorable taste, aroma, visual appeal, and consumer familiarity with these species. However, pâtés made from freshwater trout demonstrated more balanced textural characteristics, with sensory and instrumental data indicating desirable levels of hardness and spreadability.

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References

- Ahmed, I., Jan, K., Fatma, S., & Dawood, M. A. (2022). Muscle proximate composition of various food fish species and their nutritional significance: A review. *Journal of Animal Physiology and Animal Nutrition*, 106(3), 690–719. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jpn.13711>
- Aydin, C., Kurt, Ü., & Kaya, Y. (2020). Comparison of the effects of ohmic and conventional heating methods on some quality parameters of the hot-smoked fish Pâté. *Journal of Aquatic Food Product Technology*, 29(4), 407–416. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10498850.2020.1741752>
- Baechele, M., Via, M. A., Clausen, M. P., & Vilgis, T. A. (2025). Function of different emulsifiers in spreadable meat emulsions: A systematic study of physical properties. *Food Biophysics*, 20(2), 57. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11483-025-09941-2>
- Botella-Martínez, C., Pérez-Álvarez, J. Á., Fernández-López, J., & Viuda-Martos, M. (2024). Innovative formulation in pâté using a gelled emulsion of hemp oil (*Cannabis sativa* L.) as fat replacer. *LWT*, 206, 116630. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2024.116630>
- Branziari, R., Roila, R., Valiani, A., Ranucci, D., Ortenzi, R., Miraglia, D., ... & Franceschini, R. (2019). Nutritional quality, safety and sensory properties of smoked tench (*Tinca tinca*) pâté from Trasimeno Lake, Italy. *Italian Journal of Food Safety*, 8(3), 8130. <https://doi.org/10.4081/ijfs.2019.8130>
- Budhathoki, M., Campbell, D., Belton, B., Newton, R., Li, S., Zhang, W., & Little, D. (2022). Factors influencing consumption behaviour towards aquatic food among Asian consumers: a systematic scoping review. *Foods*, 11(24), 4043. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods11244043>
- Di Monaco, R., Giaccone, T., Cavella, S., & Masi, P. (2008). Predicting texture attributes from microstructural, rheological and thermal properties of hazelnut spreads. *Journal of Texture Studies*, 39, 460–479. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-4603.2008.00154.x>
- Difonzo, G., Squeo, G., Calasso, M., Pasqualone, A., & Caponio, F. (2019). Physico-chemical, microbiological and sensory evaluation of ready-to-use vegetable pâté added with olive leaf extract. *Foods*, 8(4), 138. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods8040138>
- Engelen, L., & de Wijk, R. A. (2012). Oral processing and texture perception. Food oral processing: *Fundamentals of Eating and Sensory Perception*, 8, 157–176. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781444360943.ch8>
- FAO, (2024). The state of world fisheries and aquaculture 2024—blue transformation in action. *The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture (SOFLA)*. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cd0683en>
- Fernandes, C. M., Sveinsdóttir, H. I., Tómasson, T., Arason, S., & Gudjónsdóttir, M. (2024). Influence of hot-smoking on the stability of fresh and frozen-thawed deep-skinned Atlantic mackerel fillets during cold storage. *Food Science & Nutrition*, 12(7), 4849–4864. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fsn3.4132>
- Grand View Research, (2024). Pâtés Market Size, Share & Trends Analysis Report By Product (Chicken, Duck, Fish), By Distribution Channel (Supermarkets & Hypermarkets, Online, Specialty stores), By Region (North America, Europe), And Segment Forecasts to 2024 – 2030. Retrieved from <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/pates-market>. Accessed 29.07.2025.
- Janjić, J., Mirilović, M., Vojnović, B., Đurić, S., Vujanić, T., Laudanović, M., & Baltić, B. (2024). Examination of the volume and value of fish and fish products imports into Serbia from 2012 to 2021. *Meat Technology*, 65(1), 43–51. <https://doi.org/10.18485/meattech.2024.65.1.5>
- Kim, I. A., den-Hollander, E., & Lee, H. S. (2018). Two-step rating-based ‘double-faced applicability’ test for sensory analysis of spread products as an alternative to descriptive analysis with trained panel. *Food Research International*, 105, 250–260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2017.11.048>
- Lámfalusy, T., Ózsvári, L., Szakos, D., & Kasza, G. (2025). Freshwater compared to marine fish—A quantitative study on consumer perspectives. *Aquaculture*, 603, 742382. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2025.742382>
- Lazárková, Z., Kratochvilová, A., Salek, R. N., Poláček, Z., Šiška, L., Pětová, M., & Buňka, F. (2023). Influence of

- heat treatment on the chemical, physical, microbiological and sensorial properties of pork liver *pâté* as affected by fat content. *Foods*, 12(12), 2423. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods12122423>
- Lima, T. L. S., Costa, G. F. D., Alves, R. D. N., Araújo, C. D. L. D., Silva, G. F. G. D., Ribeiro, N. L., ... & Andrade, R. O. D. (2022).** Vegetable oils in emulsified meat products: a new strategy to replace animal fat. *Food Science and Technology*, 42, e103621. <https://doi.org/10.1590/fst.103621>
- Lončarević, I., Pajin, B., Omorjan, R., Torbica, A., Zarić, D., Maksimović, J., & Švarc Gajić, J. (2013).** The influence of lecithin from different sources on crystallization and physical properties of nontrans fat. *Journal of Texture Studies*, 44(6), 450–458. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jtxs.12033>
- Mancera-Rodriguez, L., Muñoz-Ramirez, A. P., Lopez-Vargas, J. H., & Simal-Gandara, J. (2022).** Development, characterization and stability of a white cachama *pâté*-type product (*Piaractus brachypomus*). *Food Chemistry*, 375, 131660. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2021.131660>
- Martínez, E., Rabadán, A., Álvarez-Ortí, M., Mitre, J., & Pardo, J. E. (2025).** Fat reduction and lipid profile optimization in Spanish spreadable meat product using an oil-in-water emulsion. *European Food Research and Technology*, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00217-025-04682-5>
- Mielcarek, K., Puścion-Jakubik, A., Gromkowska-Kępka, K. J., Soroczyńska, J., Naliwajko, S. K., Markiewicz-Żukowska, R., ... & Socha, K. (2020).** Proximal composition and nutritive value of raw, smoked and pickled freshwater fish. *Foods*, 9(12), 1879. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods9121879>
- Nguyen, L., Gao, Z., & Anderson, J. L. (2023).** Perception shifts in seafood consumption in the United States. *Marine Policy*, 148, 105438. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2022.105438>
- Nikolić, I., Dokić, L., Rakić, D., Tomović, V., Maravić, N., Vidosavljević, S., Šereš, Z., & Šoronja-Simović, D. (2018).** The role of two types of continuous phases based on cellulose during textural, color, and sensory characterization of novel food spread with pumpkin seed flour. *Journal of Food Processing and Preservation*, 42(8), <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfpp.13684>
- Pětová, M., Poláček, Z., Lapčíková, B., Lapčík, L., Buňková, L., Pospiech, M., Foltin, P., Talár, J., Salek, R.N., Kůrová, V., Křištofová, K., & Buňka, F. (2024).** Evaluation of the viscoelastic properties of pork liver *pâté* during sterilisation observed in situ. *LWT*, 191, 115614. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2023.115614>
- Ranilović, J., Bebek, J., Tomić-Obrdalj, H., Gajari, D., & Cvetković, T. (2020).** A practical application of sensory and rheological measurement in the development of fish *pâté* quality attributes. *Hrvatski časopis za prehrambenu tehnologiju, biotehnologiju i nutricionizam*, 15(3–4), 147–151. <https://doi.org/10.31895/hcptbn.15.3-4.1>
- Regal Springs, (2025).** *What are the advantages of freshwater fish compared to saltwater fish?* Retrieved June 29, 2025, from <https://regalsprings.co.id/en/articles/what-are-the-advantages-of-freshwater-fish-compared-to-saltwater-fish/>
- Retrieved from <https://progressivemagazin.rs/online/pastete-i-namazi-3/>. Accessed 29.07.2025.
- Sensory analysis - General guidance for the design of test rooms, (2015).** (SRPS EN ISO 8589:2015) <https://iss.rs/en/project/show/iss:proj:46864>
- Sensory analysis — Guidelines for the use of quantitative response scales, (2013).** (SRPS ISO 4121:2013) <https://iss.rs/en/project/show/iss:proj:42487>
- Sensory analysis - Selection and training of sensory assessors, (2023).** (ISO 8586:2023) <https://iss.rs/en/project/show/iss:proj:69831>
- Stojanovska, T., Kalevska, T., Nikolovska Nedelkoska, D., & Pavlovska, G. (2022).** Formulation, production, and determination of physical-chemical and sensory characteristics of three different functional Ohrid trout *pâtés*. *International Journal of Food Technology and Nutrition*, 5(9–10), 103–108.
- Szczesniak, A. S. (2002).** Texture is a sensory property. *Food Quality and Preference*, 13(4), 215–225. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0950-3293\(01\)00039-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0950-3293(01)00039-8)
- Tiensa, B. E., Barbut, S., & Marangoni, A. G. (2017).** Influence of fat structure on the mechanical properties of commercial *pâté* products. *Food Research International*, 100, 558–565. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2017.07.051>
- Tilami, S. K., Sampels, S., Zajíc, T., Krejsa, J., Másilko, J., & Mráz, J. (2018).** Nutritional value of several commercially important river fish species from the Czech Republic. *PeerJ*, 6, e5729. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.5729>
- Torrissen, J. K., & Onozaka, Y. (2017).** Comparing fish to meat: Perceived qualities by food lifestyle segments. *Aquaculture Economics & Management*, 21(1), 44–70. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13657305.2017.1265022>
- Traina, A., Quinci, E. M., Sabatino, N., Del Core, M., Bellante, A., Bono, G., Giuga, M., Avellone, G., Sprovieri, M., & D'Agostino, F. (2024).** Protein, Essential Amino Acid, and Fatty Acid Composition of Five Target Fishery Species of Central Mediterranean Sea. *Animals*, 14(15), 2158. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani14152158>
- Trindade, P. C. O., Santos, B. A. D., Hollweg, G., Correa, L. P., Pinton, M. B., Padilha, M., Payeras, R. H. Z., Rosa, S. C., Cichoski, A. J., & Campagnol, P. C. B. (2023).** Pea protein isolate as a meat substitute in canned pork *pâté*: Nutritional, technological, oxidative, and sensory properties. *Foods*, 12(18), 3486. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods12183486>
- Yang, X., Saunders, A., & Mohan, M. S. (2024).** Effect of temperature on the rheological, textural, and sensory properties of butters from New Zealand market. *Journal of Texture Studies*, 55(4), e12859. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jtxs.12859>
- Yi-Li, T., Juhari, N. H., Jambari, N. N., Rozzamri, A., Nor-Khaizura, M. A. R., & Ismail-Fitry, M. R. (2025).** Tuna and tuna products: a review of the nutrition, processing, safety, and future prospects. *Fisheries Science*, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12562-025-01878-2>
- Youssef, M. K., & Barbut, S. (2010).** Effects of caseinate, whey and milk proteins on emulsified beef meat batters prepared with different protein levels. *Journal of Muscle Foods*, 21(4), 785–800. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-4573.2010.00219.x>
- Youssef, M. K., & Barbut, S. (2011).** Effects of two types of soy protein isolates, native and preheated whey protein

isolates on emulsified meat batters prepared at different protein levels. *Meat Science*, 87(1), 54–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meatsci.2010.09.002>

Zhang, W., Xiao, S., Samaraweera, H., Lee, E. J., & Ahn, D. U. (2010). Improving functional value of meat products. *Meat Science*, 86(1), 15–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meatsci.2010.04.018>

Zheng, L., Regenstein, J. M., Zhou, L., & Wang, Z. (2022). Soy protein isolates: A review of their composition,

aggregation, and gelation. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety*, 21(2), 1940–1957. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4337.12925>

Županjac, M., Ikonić, P., Šojić, B., & Đermanović, B. (2023). Physicochemical and sensory properties of pork liver pâté formulated with sunflower oleogel as fat substituent. *Meat Technology*, 64(2), 416–421. <https://doi.org/10.18485/meattech.2023.64.2.80>

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